

Elementary particle mixings as convex sums of permutations

Adolf Cusmariu

adolcus@gmail.com

A matrix is doubly stochastic if and only if it is a convex sum of permutations: Birkhoff's Theorem **[1]**.

For **2D** particle mixers this is obvious:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \cos^2\theta & \sin^2\theta \\ \sin^2\theta & \cos^2\theta \end{pmatrix} = \cos^2\theta \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} + \sin^2\theta \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

In **3D** there are six permutation matrices (as many as there are Quarks!):

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_1 &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_2 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_3 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ \pi_4 &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_5 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_6 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Together with Birkhoff's Theorem as a guide these will allow transparent recovery of the known particle mixers **[2]**, and a systematic discovery of many new exemplars almost at will.

Consistent with the 2D solution, let

$$P_{1K}(\theta_j) = c_j^2 \pi_1 + s_j^2 \pi_k \quad \text{for } k = 2, \dots, 6 \text{ and } j = 1, 2, 3.$$

As usual $c_j = \cos(\theta_j)$ and $s_j = \sin(\theta_j)$. Specifically, the $P_{1K}(\theta_j)$ building-blocks are

$$\begin{aligned} P_{12}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} & P_{13}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & P_{14}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} \\ P_{15}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} & P_{16}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

all doubly stochastic by design for any given mixing angle; recall also that the product of doubly stochastic matrices is so itself.

Now, by direct computation, the product

$$P_{14}(\theta_2)P_{13}(\theta_1)P_{14}(\theta_3)$$

yields immediately the doubly stochastic mixing matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_1^2 & c_3^2 s_1^2 & s_1^2 s_3^2 \\ c_2^2 s_1^2 & c_1^2 c_2^2 c_3^2 + s_2^2 s_3^2 & c_3^2 s_2^2 + c_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 \\ s_1^2 s_2^2 & c_1^2 c_3^2 s_2^2 + c_2^2 s_3^2 & c_2^2 c_3^2 + c_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

derived with some effort from the Kobayashi/Maskawa (KM) matrix **[2]**. Similarly, the product

$$P_{14}(\theta_2)P_{12}(\theta_3)P_{13}(\theta_1)$$

yields the probability mixing matrix arising from the Maiami/Chau/Keung (MCK) matrix **[2]**:

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_1^2 c_3^2 & c_3^2 s_1^2 & s_3^2 \\ c_2^2 s_1^2 + c_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 & c_1^2 c_2^2 + s_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 & c_3^2 s_2^2 \\ c_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 + s_1^2 s_2^2 & c_2^2 s_1^2 s_3^2 + c_1^2 s_2^2 & c_2^2 c_3^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

again effortlessly doubly stochastic by design. Ample mix-and-match options are available for equally valid outcomes. An ordering change in the (MCK) mix as

$$P_{13}(\theta_1)P_{14}(\theta_2)P_{12}(\theta_3)$$

yields the matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_1^2 c_3^2 + s_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 & s_1^2 c_2^2 & c_1^2 s_3^2 + c_3^2 s_1^2 s_2^2 \\ c_3^2 s_1^2 + c_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 & c_1^2 c_2^2 & s_1^2 s_3^2 + c_1^2 s_2^2 c_3^2 \\ c_2^2 s_3^2 & s_2^2 & c_2^2 c_3^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

not obviously derivable by inspection from its neighbor above. More exemplars:

$$P_{14}(\theta_2)P_{12}(\theta_3)P_{15}(\theta_1)$$

where $P_{13}(\theta_1)$ was replaced by $P_{15}(\theta_1)$ in the (MCK) mix, to yield

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_1^2 c_3^2 + s_1^2 s_3^2 & c_3^2 s_1^2 & c_1^2 s_3^2 \\ c_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 + c_3^2 s_1^2 s_2^2 & c_1^2 c_2^2 + s_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 & c_1^2 c_3^2 s_2^2 + c_2^2 s_1^2 \\ c_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 + c_2^2 c_3^2 s_1^2 & c_1^2 s_2^2 + c_2^2 s_1^2 s_3^2 & c_1^2 c_2^2 c_3^2 + s_1^2 s_2^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Next,

$$P_{12}(\theta_3)P_{14}(\theta_1)P_{16}(\theta_2)$$

leads to

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 + c_2^2 c_3^2 & c_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 + s_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 & c_2^2 s_1^2 s_3^2 + c_3^2 s_2^2 \\ c_1^2 c_3^2 s_2^2 + c_2^2 s_3^2 & c_1^2 c_2^2 c_3^2 + c_3^2 s_1^2 s_2^2 & c_2^2 c_3^2 s_1^2 + s_2^2 s_3^2 \\ s_1^2 s_2^2 & c_1^2 s_2^2 + c_2^2 s_1 & c_1^2 c_2^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Finally

$$P_{14}(\theta_1)P_{15}(\theta_2)P_{16}(\theta_3)$$

yields

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_2^2 c_3^2 + s_2^2 s_3^2 & c_3^2 s_2^2 & c_2^2 s_3^2 \\ c_3^2 s_1^2 s_2^2 + c_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 & c_1^2 c_2^2 c_3^2 + s_3^2 (c_1^2 s_2^2 + c_2^2 s_1^2) & s_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 + c_3^2 (c_1^2 s_2^2 + c_2^2 s_1^2) \\ c_3^2 c_1^2 s_2^2 + s_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 & s_1^2 c_2^2 c_3^2 + s_3^2 (c_1^2 c_2^2 + s_2^2 s_1^2) & c_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 + c_3^2 (c_1^2 c_2^2 + s_1^2 s_2^2) \end{pmatrix}$$

There seems to be no algebraic reason to prefer one mixing exemplar over another; numerical outcomes do differ, particularly off-diagonal for Quark mixing, and more dramatically for Neutrinos. To simplify the display in the numerical table below, a left-column heading (142/131/143) means the mixing blocks were

$$P_{14}(\theta_2)P_{13}(\theta_1)P_{14}(\theta_3)$$

and so on. The standard mixing angles **[2]** were used as appropriate; the probabilities are shown in percentages, to three decimals of precision.

Triplet	Quarks			Neutrinos		
(142/131/143)	94.909	5.091	0.000	69.681	29.650	0.669
	5.082	94.744	0.174	0.945	42.259	56.796
	0.088	0.165	99.826	1.259	55.585	43.155
(142/123/131)	94.908	5.091	0.001	68.144	29.650	2.205
	5.082	94.745	0.017	23.689	51.819	24.491
	0.009	0.164	99.826	18.326	63.297	18.377
(131/142/123)	94.908	5.082	0.001	78.040	12.997	8.962
	5.090	94.745	0.016	34.077	41.923	24.000
	0.001	0.017	99.826	24.491	57.131	18.377
(142/123/151)	94.908	5.091	0.001	68.813	29.650	1.537
	0.008	94.745	5.245	30.169	39.767	30.063
	5.083	0.016	94.753	22.638	47.235	30.127
(123/141/162)	99.826	0.000	0.174	42.643	1.080	56.277
	0.164	94.754	5.082	39.809	47.193	12.997
	0.172	0.344	99.484	38.484	20.998	40.518
(141/152/163)	99.826	0.172	0.001	43.183	55.872	0.945
	0.009	94.744	5.245	17.598	30.377	52.025
	0.163	5.083	94.753	24.491	25.076	50.432

Again, any doubly stochastic matrix is a convex sum of permutations; thus the scaling weights in the more general product

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{1k}(\theta_1)P_{1m}(\theta_2)P_{1n}(\theta_3) &= (c_1^2 \pi_1 + s_1^2 \pi_k)(c_2^2 \pi_1 + s_2^2 \pi_m)(c_3^2 \pi_1 + s_3^2 \pi_n) \\
&= c_1^2 c_2^2 c_3^2 \pi_1 + c_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 \pi_n + c_1^2 s_2^2 c_3^2 \pi_m + c_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 \pi_m \pi_n + \\
&+ s_1^2 c_2^2 c_3^2 \pi_k + s_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 \pi_k \pi_n + s_1^2 s_2^2 c_3^2 \pi_k \pi_m + s_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 \pi_k \pi_m \pi_n
\end{aligned}$$

are indeed a convex set:

$$\begin{aligned}
&c_1^2 c_2^2 c_3^2 + c_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 + c_1^2 s_2^2 c_3^2 + c_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 + s_1^2 c_2^2 c_3^2 + s_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 + \\
&s_1^2 s_2^2 c_3^2 + s_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 = (c_1^2 + s_1^2)(c_2^2 + s_2^2)(c_3^2 + s_3^2) = 1
\end{aligned}$$

In fact, this entire octet

$$\left\{ C_1^2 C_2^2 C_3^2, C_1^2 C_2^2 S_3^2, C_1^2 S_2^2 C_3^2, C_1^2 S_2^2 S_3^2, S_1^2 C_2^2 C_3^2, S_1^2 C_2^2 S_3^2, S_1^2 S_2^2 C_3^2, S_1^2 S_2^2 S_3^2 \right\}$$

is needed to build mixers with any members from the permutation set $\{\pi_1, \dots, \pi_6\}$. For example, the combination above with $k = 2$, $m = 3$, and $n = 4$, with help from the Cayley table

*	π_2	π_3	π_4	π_5	π_6
π_2	π_1	π_6	π_5	π_4	π_3
π_3	π_5	π_1	π_6	π_2	π_4
π_4	π_6	π_5	π_1	π_3	π_2
π_6	π_4	π_2	π_3	π_1	π_5
π_5	π_3	π_4	π_2	π_6	π_1

works out as

$$C_1^2 C_2^2 C_3^2 \pi_1 + C_1^2 C_2^2 S_3^2 \pi_4 + C_1^2 S_2^2 C_3^2 \pi_3 + C_1^2 S_2^2 S_3^2 \pi_6 + S_1^2 C_2^2 C_3^2 \pi_2 + S_1^2 C_2^2 S_3^2 \pi_5 + S_1^2 S_2^2 C_3^2 \pi_6 + S_1^2 S_2^2 S_3^2 \pi_3$$

which generates yet another exemplar

$$\begin{pmatrix} C_1^2 C_2^2 & S_1^2 S_3^2 + C_1^2 C_3^2 S_2^2 & S_1^2 C_3^2 + C_1^2 S_3^2 S_2^2 \\ S_2^2 & C_2^2 C_3^2 & C_2^2 S_3^2 \\ C_2^2 S_1^2 & C_1^2 S_3^2 + C_3^2 S_2^2 S_1^2 & C_1^2 C_3^2 + S_1^2 S_2^2 S_3^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

not immediately recognizable in this 'assembled' equivalent, though doubly stochastic for free.

For general reference, the table below lists pairings of octets and permutations for a few exemplars.

	$C_1^2 C_2^2 C_3^2$	$C_1^2 C_2^2 S_3^2$	$C_1^2 C_3^2 S_2^2$	$C_1^2 S_2^2 S_3^2$	$C_2^2 C_3^2 S_1^2$	$C_2^2 S_1^2 S_3^2$	$C_3^2 S_1^2 S_2^2$	$S_1^2 S_2^2 S_3$
142/131/143	π_1	π_4	π_3	π_6	π_3	π_6	π_5	π_2
142/123/131	π_1	π_3	π_2	π_6	π_4	π_5	π_6	π_2
131/142/123	π_1	π_2	π_4	π_6	π_3	π_5	π_6	π_4
142/123/151	π_1	π_5	π_2	π_4	π_4	π_3	π_6	π_1
123/141/162	π_1	π_6	π_4	π_2	π_2	π_3	π_5	π_1
141/152/163	π_1	π_6	π_5	π_1	π_4	π_2	π_3	π_4
121/132/143	π_1	π_4	π_3	π_6	π_2	π_5	π_6	π_3
151/132/143	π_1	π_4	π_3	π_6	π_5	π_2	π_4	π_1

Now, a more general way to build such doubly stochastic matrices is to use the blocks

$$P_{nK}(\theta_1) = C_1^2 \pi_n + S_1^2 \pi_k \quad \text{for } n, k = 1, \dots, 6$$

$$P_{mq}(\theta_2) = C_2^2 \pi_m + S_2^2 \pi_q \quad \text{for } m, q = 1, \dots, 6$$

$$P_{sv}(\theta_3) = C_3^2 \pi_s + S_3^2 \pi_v \quad \text{for } s, v = 1, \dots, 6$$

and form the product

$$P_{nK}(\theta_1) P_{mq}(\theta_2) P_{sv}(\theta_3)$$

for selected indices, generating a plethora of mixing matrices. Alternatively, since this product equals

$$C_1^2 C_2^2 C_3^2 \pi_n \pi_m \pi_s + C_1^2 C_2^2 S_3^2 \pi_n \pi_m \pi_v + C_1^2 C_3^2 S_2^2 \pi_n \pi_q \pi_s + \\ C_1^2 S_2^2 S_3^2 \pi_n \pi_q \pi_v + C_2^2 C_3^2 S_1^2 \pi_k \pi_m \pi_s + C_2^2 S_1^2 S_3^2 \pi_k \pi_m \pi_v + \\ C_3^2 S_1^2 S_2^2 \pi_k \pi_q \pi_s + S_1^2 S_2^2 S_3^2 \pi_k \pi_q \pi_v$$

the Cayley table will help work out the convex sum - and then the actual matrix - once indices have been chosen; this scaling octet is identical of course to that listed above.

Finally, substitution of hyperbolic variables into the original building blocks

$$N_{1K}(\theta_j) = \cosh_j^2 \pi_1 - \sinh_j^2 \pi_k \quad \text{for } k = 2, \dots, 6 \quad \text{and } j = 1, 2, 3.$$

will not alter their doubly stochastic nature, nor of the mixers; however, elements will no longer be conventional probabilities, but 'signed' measures [5]. For example, let now

$$\text{ch}_j = \cosh(\theta_j) \text{ and } \text{sh}_j = \sinh(\theta_j)$$

The 'signed' hyperbolic blocks are

$$\mathbf{N}_{12}(\theta_1) = \begin{pmatrix} \text{ch}_1^2 & 0 & -\text{sh}_1^2 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\text{sh}_1^2 & 0 & \text{ch}_1^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \mathbf{N}_{13}(\theta_2) = \begin{pmatrix} \text{ch}_2^2 & -\text{sh}_2^2 & 0 \\ -\text{sh}_2^2 & \text{ch}_2^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \mathbf{N}_{14}(\theta_3) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \text{ch}_3^2 & -\text{sh}_3^2 \\ 0 & -\text{sh}_3^2 & \text{ch}_3^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

so the product $\mathbf{N}_{12}(\theta_1)\mathbf{N}_{13}(\theta_2)\mathbf{N}_{14}(\theta_3)$ leads to

$$\begin{pmatrix} \text{ch}_1^2\text{ch}_2^2 & \text{sh}_1^2\text{sh}_3^2 - \text{ch}_1\text{ch}_3^2\text{sh}_2^2 & -\text{sh}_1^2\text{ch}_3^2 + \text{ch}_1^2\text{sh}_3^2\text{sh}_2^2 \\ -\text{sh}_2^2 & \text{ch}_2^2\text{ch}_3^2 & -\text{ch}_2^2\text{sh}_3^2 \\ -\text{ch}_2^2\text{sh}_1^2 & -\text{ch}_1^2\text{sh}_3^2 + \text{ch}_3^2\text{sh}_2^2\text{sh}_1^2 & \text{ch}_1^2\text{ch}_3^2 - \text{sh}_1^2\text{sh}_2^2\text{sh}_3^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Numerical results are shown below side-by-side for standard Quark mixing angles.

$$\begin{array}{cc} \mathbf{P}_{12}(\theta_1)\mathbf{P}_{13}(\theta_2)\mathbf{P}_{14}(\theta_3) & \mathbf{N}_{12}(\theta_1)\mathbf{N}_{13}(\theta_2)\mathbf{N}_{14}(\theta_3) \\ \begin{pmatrix} 0.900773 & 0.048450 & 0.050778 \\ 0.050909 & 0.900773 & 0.048318 \\ 0.048318 & 0.050778 & 0.900905 \end{pmatrix} & \begin{pmatrix} 1.108173 & -0.055622 & -0.052552 \\ -0.052698 & 1.108173 & -0.055475 \\ -0.055475 & -0.052552 & 1.108027 \end{pmatrix} \end{array}$$

Hybrids between trigonometric and hyperbolic building blocks are obviously possible; mixing matrices between particles and anti-particles built from hyperbolic or hybrid blocks is intriguing.

References

- [1] R. Horn, C. Johnson, 'Matrix Analysis', 2nd edition (2013), Cambridge U P, p. 549.
- [2] A. Cusmariu, 'Mixing strategies and Hadamard products in elementary particle physics', zenodo.8404365, 2023.
- [3] Wikipedia article on 'Cabbibo-Kobayashi-Maskawa matrix'.
- [4] Wikipedia article on 'Pontecorvo-Maki-Nakagawa-Sakata matrix'.
- [5] M. Loeve, 'Probability Theory', Van Nostrand Reinhold, 3rd Edition (1963)